

Analysing the Serum Amounts of Trace Metals Such as Zinc, Copper, Manganese, and Magnesium in Patients with Liver CirrhosisVishnu Sain¹, Jaya Jain², Ashutosh Jain³, Prachi Sharma⁴, Shilpa Srivastava⁵¹PhD Scholar, Department of Biochemistry, Index Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Indore.²Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Index Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Indore.³Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Index Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Indore⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Public Health Dentistry, Mahatma Gandhi Dental College and Hospital, Jaipur Rajasthan⁵Associate professor, Department of Oral pathology and Microbiology Mahatma Gandhi Dental College and Hospital Jaipur

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Abstract:**Background:** Trace elements contribute in a multitude of physiological as well as metabolic processes in humans, regardless of their source. For roughly one quarter of the body's enzymes to accomplish their metabolic tasks, metal ions have to trigger them. It is yet unclear how trace elements contribute to the creation of liver cirrhosis and its ramifications.**Materials and Methods:** By applying a plasma sequential spectrophotometer, the serum amounts of zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium were determined in 96 unaffected volunteers and 96 unhealthy individuals that is suffering from alcoholic liver cirrhosis. Statistical analysis employing Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric tests were carried out to evaluate the serum amounts of these trace elements amongst the individuals of both the groups.**Results:** Zinc levels in serum in liver cirrhosis sufferers were substantially lower than in controls ($P < 0.001$). Patients with liver cirrhosis exhibited significantly higher serum amounts of manganese and copper with the value of $P < 0.001$. Between individuals suffering from liver cirrhosis and controls, there was no discernible difference in the magnesium levels ($P = 0.126$). Zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium concentrations were similar in patients with liver cirrhosis who were male or female. The only factor that varied substantially ($P = 0.027$) across the Child-Pugh groups was the manganese concentration. Compared to cirrhotic individuals without encephalopathy, patients with hepatic encephalopathy had significantly lower zinc concentrations ($P = 0.002$).**Conclusion:** Optimizing the amount of trace elements may help forestall complications and maybe reduce the beginning of liver cirrhosis. It would be advisable to routinely offer trace element analysis.**Keywords:** Zinc, Copper, Manganese, Magnesium, Liver Cirrhosis, Trace Elements.

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Introduction

Uncertainty persists regarding the involvement of trace elements in the etiology of liver cirrhosis and its consequences. Hepatocellular necrosis is the first event that occurs in fibrogenesis. Hepatocellular necrosis may be triggered in the early stages by reactive oxygen radicals, proteinases, and inflammatory cell products, which will then cause a cascade of cytokines to be released. Increase in extracellular matrix, stellate cell activation, rough endoplasmic reticulum, and smooth muscle specific α -actin expression become apparent after hepatic damage [1]. Essential trace

elements magnesium, zinc, copper, manganese, and manganese are still being researched in the context of liver cirrhosis and its related complications. The role of trace elements has been extensively studied in recent years in various cancer types, such as breast, gastric, lung, oral, and pancreatic, as well as in liver cirrhosis. Trace elements are vital for functioning of numerous enzymes, and therefore, variations in the serum amounts of these biochemical markers may be connected to the pathogenesis of various cancers.[2]

Evidence pertaining to serum amounts in liver cirrhosis patients are inconclusive. More than 300 enzymatic systems are connected to zinc. Cu-Zn superoxide dismutase, an enzyme made of zinc, boosts the body's defense against reactive oxygen radicals. Zinc has several functions, including anti-inflammatory, anti-apoptotic, membrane and cytoskeletal stabilization, anti-oxidant, and crucial co-factor in DNA synthesis [3]. Being involved in numerous enzymatic activities, copper is an integral trace metal. Copper is primarily involved in redox reactions. [4] Reactive copper can either directly or indirectly aid in liver injury by rousing Kupfer cells. The detrimental consequences of copper are generally acknowledged to be associated with oxidative stress [5].

Manganese is an activator of plenty of enzymes implicated in the Krebs cycle, notably those responsible for participating in decarboxilation. The creation of proteins, the activation of enzymes, oxidative phosphorylation, renal potassium exchange, hydrogen exchange, and other functions all depend on magnesium. The current research aimed to investigate serum amounts of various trace elements, including zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium, in patients with liver cirrhosis while contrasting them with unaffected volunteers, as these elements could potentially have a role in the genesis of cirrhotic consequences.

Materials and Methods

The research study comprised 96 hospitalized patients, with liver cirrhosis of ethylic etiology detected between 2020 and 2023. Ninety-six unaffected healthy people were also enrolled in the current investigation. All research volunteers provided their informed permission. Ethics Committee accorded its approval to the study protocol. The protocol was adhered to abide with the Helsinki Declaration's standards of conduct.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Liver cirrhosis (able to sign an informed consent form, laboratory and pathohistological accomplishments, evidence of viral hepatitis, and normal ceruloplasmine assessments), along with anamnestic data on alcohol intake across the age range of 18 and 70. Vegetarianism, Wilson's illness, cancer, acute liver failure, diminished renal function (creatinine clearance <60 ml/min), multiorgan failure, and unwillingness to sign an informed consent were the exclusion criteria.

Sample Size Estimation: A fifty percent population share was determined as multiple studies depicted variable population proportion. Keep in mind that the margin of error is presumed to be 11% and that z is 1.96 at the level of confidence of 95%.

The formula stated below is implemented to calculate the sample size, that is,

$$n = z^2 \times \hat{p} (1 - \hat{p}) / \varepsilon^2$$

wherein

z is the z score

ε is the margin of error

N is the population size

$\hat{p}$ is the population proportion

The outcome of $n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)/(0.11)^2$ was 79.37.

In each group, we investigated 96 respondents.

There were two major groups as following:

Group I which comprises of 96 affected people (suffering from liver cirrhosis)

Group II which comprises of 96 unaffected healthy volunteers' group (controls).

Patients with liver cirrhosis (group I) were classified into Child-Pugh A, B, and C groups based on the Child-Pugh classification. Each Child-Pugh group comprised thirty-two individuals. All the individuals underwent laboratory analysis as a component of comprehensive medical examinations.

Methods

Anticoagulants were not administered during the acquisition of blood samples, and serum was preserved refrigerated at -20°C until the next step. 0.5 ml of 30% H₂O₂ and 1.5 ml of concentrated nitric acid were added while processing after 1 ml of serum was taken into account for digestion. Following digestion, the sample was allowed to chill for twenty minutes. Ultra clean water was incorporated to the solution after it was moved into a 10 ml container. Thermo Jarrell Ash, USA's TraceScan plasma sequential spectrophotometer has been utilized to gauge the proportions of trace elements.

Analytical Statistics: Non-parametric tests like Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis have been employed to analyze the data, which were displayed with a median and a 5–95 percentile range. MedCalc software (MedCalc Software, Mariakerke, Belgium) was implemented for statistics. $P < 0.05$ was the threshold for significance.

Results

Table 1 illustrates the serum values for zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium in liver cirrhosis patients and controls. Zinc levels in patients with cirrhosis of the liver were substantially lower than those in normal. Between patients with the condition and controls, there was no discernible differ-

ence in the magnesium levels. Male and female patients with liver cirrhosis did not differ in the

amounts of zinc, copper, manganese, or magnesium (Table 2).

Table 1: Depicts the serum amounts of zinc, copper, manganese and magnesium in individuals with liver cirrhosis and unaffected people

Trace elements	Affected individuals group I Subjects(N=96)	Unaffected people group II volunteers(N=96)	Statistics	
			Z	P
Zinc($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	0.78(0.19–1.69)	10.17(8.17–14.06)	10.01	<0.001
Copper($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	22(11.17–30.56)	13(11.17–19.99)	-7.70	<0.001
Manganese($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	2.5(0.05–29.69)	0.04(0.01–0.42)	-8.0	<0.001
Magnesium(mmol/L)	0.99(0.59–1.39)	0.9(0.60–1.08)	-1.46	0.126

Table 2: Exhibiting the serum amounts of zinc, copper, manganese and magnesium in male and female individuals with liver cirrhosis

Trace elements	Male volunteers group I(N=96)	Female volunteers group I(N=96)	Statistics	
			Z	P
Zinc ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	0.78(0.25–1.66)	0.66(0.20–1.99)	-0.30	0.746
Copper($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	21.20(9.90–30.10)	23.56(15.49–32.12)	1.63	0.107
Manganese($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	2.14(0.04–31.16)	3.70(0.08–29.55)	1.49	0.150
Magnesium(mmol/L)	0.99(0.60–1.44)	0.88(0.71–1.36)	-1.08	0.288

Table 3 illustrates the significant difference in the serum amounts of manganese between the Child-Pugh groups (H=9.17, P=0.027). Further investigation revealed that, compared to patients with Child-Pugh A (1.98 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, P=0.002) and B liver cirrhosis (2.14 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), patients with Child-

Pugh C liver cirrhosis had considerably higher serum levels of manganese (6.25 $\mu\text{mol/L}$). There was no discernible difference in the amounts of zinc, copper, and magnesium between the Child-Pugh groups (Table 3).

Table 3: Exhibiting the serum levels of trace elements in child Pugh groups.

Trace elements	Child-Pugh A(N=32)	Child-Pugh B (N=32)	Child-Pugh C (N=32)	Statistics	
				H	P
Zinc ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.06(0.38–1.49)	0.78(0.26–1.94)	0.54(0.14–1.45)	19.24	0.053
Copper($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	19.98(13.75–29.84)	22.30(10.51–31.65)	23.20(9.75–29.76)	1.00	0.608
Manganese($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.98(0.12–9.42)	2.14(0.01–27.62)	6.25(0.01–35.75)	9.17	0.027
Magnesium(mmol/L)	0.93(0.65–1.18)	0.96(0.65–1.38)	0.88(0.40–1.53)	5.34	0.084

Table 4 depicts the serum readings for zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium in individuals with cirrhosis accompanied by hepatic encephalopathy and those who do not. In contrast to cirrhotic people without encephalopathy, patients with hepatic encephalopathy exhibited a substantially lower zinc content. The serum concentrations of other trace elements did not differ between the

encephalopathy-positive and -negative patients. Table 5 illustrates the serum amounts of zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium in individuals with cirrhosis who have ascites or not. The only substance where patients with and without ascites differed significantly in concentration was manganese.

Table 4: Exhibiting the serum amounts of zinc, copper, manganese and magnesium in individuals in cirrhosis with or without hepatic encephalopathy

Trace elements	Without encephalopathy group I(N=75)	With encephalopathy group I(N=21)	Statistics	
			Z	P
Zinc ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.01 (0.25–1.77)	0.46(0.19–1.11)	-3.09	0.002
Copper($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	21.62(13.07–31.43)	21.31(9.85–29.31)	-1.24	0.234
Manganese($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	2.22(0.01–31.38)	4.06(0.01–26.94)	0.66	0.511
Magnesium(mmol/L)	0.99(0.63–1.36)	0.98(0.53–1.37)	-1.74	0.089

Table 5: Exhibiting the serum amounts of zinc, copper, manganese and magnesium in individuals in cirrhosis with or without ascites

Tracelements	Without ascites group I(N=40)	With ascites group I(N=56)	Statistics	
			Z	P
Zinc ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.04(0.36–1.57)	0.74(0.18–1.78)	1.81	0.083
Copper($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	20.29(11.84–30.47)	22.36(10.74–30.82)	–0.28	0.784
Manganese($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.84(0.01–11.20)	4.14(0.01–31.80)	–3.44	<0.001
Magnesium(mmol/L)	0.94(0.64–1.13)	0.98(0.54–1.46)	–0.62	0.569

Discussion

Mechanisms linked on ethanol metabolism, especially oxidative stress, redox potentials and acetaldehyde, participate in the emergence of liver damage. Trace elements act as vital in oxidative stress and redox potentials. A possible role of zinc, copper, manganese and magnesium in pathogenesis of liver cirrhosis and its complications is still subject of researches.

Liver damage is an outcome of mechanisms linked to ethanol metabolism, specifically oxidative stress, redox potentials, and acetaldehyde. In conjunction with oxidative stress and redox potentials, trace elements are fundamental. Research is still ongoing to ascertain whether zinc, copper, manganese, and magnesium play a part in the genesis of liver cirrhosis and its ramifications. In the present investigation, people who had liver cirrhosis exhibited serum zinc levels that were substantially reduced than those of unaffected group of people. The findings corroborate the outcomes of Kugelmans' research [6], which linked low zinc levels to decreased protein intake, higher loss in the digestive system as a result of diarrhea or intestinal malabsorption, and increased losses by means of urination.

Their homeostasis may be mediated by the way in which that zinc and copper interact during intestinal absorption, as well as by their rivalry for binding sites on carrier proteins and cellular uptake. Perhaps this explains why copper and zinc concentrations are inverse. The serum concentration of zinc may be regulated by the relative quantities of albumin, transferrin, and metalloproteins, as zinc binds to these proteins in the cell [7]. Patients with liver cirrhosis were found to have a considerably higher serum copper content than the control group. The part that copper plays in the redox process could help to understand it.

Toxic hydroxyl radicals can be synthesized via the redox cycling of Cu^{2+} and Cu^{1+} . It is widely recognized that oxidative stress and redox mechanisms are key players in the pathophysiology of liver cirrhosis. Patients with cirrhosis had serum concentrations of manganese that were substantially greater than those of controls. Higher serum manganese levels were also seen in cirrhotic patients in studies by Krieger [8]. There was no

discernible variation in manganese concentrations between cirrhotic patients and controls, according to Moscarello's research [9]. Ultimately, manganese levels in serum appear to be higher in liver cirrhosis patients than in healthy individuals.

Since manganese is secreted in bile, an increase in manganese concentration in cholestatic liver disease may account for some of the reasons why manganese accumulation is common in liver cirrhosis⁸. It has been identified that a mechanism that may take into account for patients' manganese accumulation in the pallidum could involve a decrease in biliary excretion and an increase in systemic availability as an outcome of portosystemic shunting; intrahepatic shunting or portosystemic shunting may also have an additional effect on manganese accumulation. Manganese accumulation in the brain was confirmed by several clinical trials [8].

There was no statistically significant variation in the magnesium serum concentrations between cirrhotic patients and unaffected people of group II. In current investigation, individuals with liver cirrhosis had reduced serum magnesium levels compared to patients with hepatic steatosis and unaffected people. Furthermore, the findings of Rocchi's [10] investigation supported this. Lower magnesium values in liver cirrhosis patients were not supported by our findings. This could be partially explained by spironolactone's effect on magnesium levels. Specifically, in Stergiou's research [11], spironolactone counteracted the furosemide's magnesuric impact in cirrhotic patients and reduced magnesium excretion in urine among healthy people.

Spironolactone is the most common medication used in our patients with liver cirrhosis; yet, there were no changes observed between the spironolactone-taking and non-spironolactone-taking individuals. According to the Child-Pugh classification, patients with a more severe clinical condition of liver cirrhosis had slightly lower serum zinc concentrations; however, these differences were not statistically significant in our study. It has been hypothesised that when hepatic fibrosis advances in grade, the concentration of zinc in the serum will decrease since zinc is bound to albumin in the blood [12]. Zinc levels are lower in patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis than

in those with compensated cirrhosis, according to Yoshida's research. Serum zinc levels, however, did not significantly vary between hepatic fibrosis grades in Hatano's research [12].

Copper levels in Hatano's investigation as well as the three Child-Pugh groups in the present investigation were equivalent (Table 3). Compared to individuals with Child-Pugh A and B liver cirrhosis, those with Child-Pugh C liver cirrhosis had greater serum manganese levels. Our discoveries go contradictory to those of Spahr's investigation, which indicated that all three Child-Pugh groups had comparable manganese components. Due to advanced intrahepatic and portosystemic shunting, patients with severe liver cirrhosis appear to exhibit greater manganese concentrations. The magnesium levels across all Child-Pugh groups in our study were equivalent. The comparable levels of compensated and decompensated liver cirrhosis are likewise confirmed by Moscarella's research.

Riggio, however, discovered that hepatic encephalopathy is unaffected by short-term zinc supplementation [14]. All things considered, zinc supplementation may benefit hepatic encephalopathy; however, more research is required before this finding is used to treatment. Contrary to Krieger's [8] findings, there was no significant difference in manganese levels between individuals with liver cirrhosis and hepatic encephalopathy and those without encephalopathy. They discovered elevated manganese concentrations and proposed that individuals with liver cirrhosis would benefit from either preventing accumulation of manganese or reducing its content. Manganese concentrations in the basal ganglia of cirrhotic patients were reported to be higher than those in controls by Rose [15] and Layrargues [16].

In the present investigation, cirrhotic patients with ascites had substantially higher manganese concentrations compared to those without ascites. Zinc, copper, and magnesium levels were within the range that was appropriate. Thus, it is imperative to investigate the potential involvement of manganese in the development of ascites in patients suffering from liver cirrhosis. Lastly, reduced serum zinc concentrations and elevated manganese levels in liver cirrhosis patients may play a significant role in the etiology of liver cirrhosis and its sequelae, particularly hepatic encephalopathy. Hepatic encephalopathy may improve with zinc supplementation.

Patients suffering from hepatic encephalopathy and liver cirrhosis may benefit neurologically from the reduction in manganese levels. Higher manganese concentrations in cirrhotic individuals with ascites prompt more investigation into manganese's potential involvement in the etiology of ascites in

patients with liver cirrhosis. Perhaps lowering manganese levels will also help avoid or reduce the amount of ascites. In context of all of that, it would be advisable to routinely offer laboratory examination of trace elements since it might potentially slow the advancement of the disease and help with some of the difficulties associated with liver cirrhosis.

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